

PID36934_ChristianBihun_Oxygen_SDA

Version 1

Description

To share all data collected during a research visit to Kristineberg Marine Research Center, which includes respirometry experiments designed to investigate the effects of oxygen saturation on specific dynamic action.

Funder

Grant

Researchers

Christian Bihun (0000-0002-3992-6236)

Organizations

University of Gothenburg, Trent University

1. Main Info

Title of Plan: [PID36934_ChristianBihun_Oxygen_SDA](#)

Description:

To share all data collected during a research visit to Kristineberg Marine Research Center, which includes respirometry experiments designed to investigate the effects of oxygen saturation on specific dynamic action.

Researchers:

[Christian Bihun \(0000-0002-3992-6236\)](#)

Organizations:

[University of Gothenburg](#)

[Trent University](#)

Contact: [Bihun Christian \(Christianj.bihun@gmail.com\)](mailto:Christianj.bihun@gmail.com)

Access: [Public](#)

2. Ethics

Introduction:

3. Dataset descriptions

Introduction:

These data include raw respirometry files (unedited), cleaned respirometry files (contains only time-oxygen or time-temperature), metadata (details for each trial), and a read.me text file with descriptions for all columns.

Descriptions

[AQUASERV](#) | [all categories](#) | [generic template](#)

This data management plan will outline the results of study PID 36934 - Effects of Hyperoxia and Elevated Temperature on Specific Dynamic Action and Food Intake in European Flounder

Template: AQUASERV | all categories | generic template

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.

No

We will use these data in a single manuscript. We have no plans to re-use the data

1.1.2 What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?

We will primarily produce respirometry data (time series of oxygen consumption). The respirometry software exports these as a .txt files. The associated study details (body mass, fish ID, dates, notes, etc.) will be shared in an excel spreadsheet. We will also share fish husbandry data (temperature loggers) as .xlsx files.

1.1.3 What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?

Measuring postprandial oxygen consumption of fishes under variable oxygen saturation is central to the hypothesis in the proposed study.

1.1.4 What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?

The raw respirometry files are about 3.75 GB. All data files together should be well under 10GB.

1.1.5 What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?

Generated novel data measured by a Firesting Oxygen Reader.

1.1.6 To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

Fish physiologists or aquaculturists who are interested in the effects of hyperoxia on fish digestion.

2 FAIR data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

2.1.1 Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?

Yes

2.1.2 Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

Yes

The metadata will be in a custom format as they relate to the statistical analysis (i.e., the metadata file is imported into R for analysis).

2.1.4 Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

No

2.2 Making data accessible

2.2.1 Repository

2.2.1.1 Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?

Yes. I will upload all data to my account on Figshare, where I have published all my data from previous academic projects:

https://figshare.com/authors/Christian_Bihun/17959901

2.2.1.2 Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?

Figshare is free and available to everyone.

2.2.1.3 Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

This platform provides a DOI and citation. Once published it cannot be edited.

2.2.2 Data

2.2.2.1 Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.

All data will be made openly available.

2.2.2.2 If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

No need for an embargo.

2.2.2.4 If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?

No restrictions

2.2.2.5 How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

There will be no way of knowing who accesses the data. A download counter is provided on the Figshare page.

2.2.3 Metadata

2.2.3.1 Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?

Yes

2.2.3.2 How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?

The data will remain available forever.

2.2.3.3 Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Yes

I will include the R code used to analyze the data such that the statistical results are 100% reproducible. All software and associated packages are freely available.

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

I will provide a READ.ME text file with definitions for all scientific jargon. Units will be specified for all metrics.

2.3.2 In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?

We will use standard terminology and provide definitions and units.

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?

Readme

2.4.2 Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

CC by 4.0

2.4.5 Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.

We will ensure the results are reproducible with a well-annotated R script.

3 Data security

3.1 Data security

3.1.1 What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?

Data are backed up on the cloud services provided by my home institution (Trent University / Microsoft). I also have several physical copies.

3.1.2 Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

Yes

4 Other research outputs

4.1 Making other research outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

4.1.1 Will other research outputs be identified by a persistent identifier?

Yes

We will aim to publish the findings in an open-access journal, should they be accepted.

4.1.2 Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

Yes

The metadata sheet will be a custom excel file. There is no standard protocol for respirometry data or analyses.

4.1.4 Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

Yes

4.2 Making other research outputs accessible

4.2.2 Other research outputs

4.2.2.2 If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research outputs should be made available as soon as possible.

Not needed.

4.2.2.4 If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the other research outputs, both during and after the end of the project?

We will ensure all research outputs are open-access by choosing an appropriate journal.

4.2.2.5 How will the identity of the person accessing the other research outputs be ascertained?

There will be no way of knowing who accesses the research outputs.

4.2.2.6 Is there a need for an other research output access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive other research output)?

No

4.2.3 Metadata

4.2.3.1 Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the other research outputs?

Yes

4.2.3.2 How long will the other research outputs remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after other research outputs is no longer available?

Forever.

4.2.3.3 Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the other research outputs be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Research outputs will cite all softwares used.

4.3 Making other research outputs interoperable

4.3.1 What other research outputs and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your other research outputs interoperable to allow other research outputs exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

n/a

4.3.2 In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?

n/a

4.3.3 Will your other research outputs include qualified references to other research outputs (e.g. other research outputs from your project, or other research outputs from previous research)?

n/a

4.4 Increase other research outputs re-use

4.4.1 How will you provide documentation needed to validate other research outputs analysis and facilitate other research outputs re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, research outputs cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?

n/a

4.4.5 Describe all relevant other research outputs quality assurance processes.

Research outputs will be peer-reviewed.

5 Allocation of resources

5.1 Allocation of resources

5.1.1 What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.) ?

Indirect cost

5.1.2 How will these be covered?

I do not foresee any costs.

5.1.3 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

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6 Ethics

6.1 Ethics

6.1.1 Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

No

6.1.2 Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

No

7 Other issues

7.1 Other issues

7.1.1 Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

No

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